

CHARACTERISATION OF RESIN FLOW AND VOID FORMATION IN RFI

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ABSTRACT

Resin flow and void formation at the surface of composite lay-ups were monitored during the manufacturing of laminates using resin film infusion (RFI). Two manufacturing methods were compared: bulk and interleaved RFI. Bulk RFI featured a lay-up consisting of distinct stacks of resin and textile plies before infusion while interleaved RFI featured a lay-up where textile plies were interleaved with resin films. The effects of textile architecture and resin viscosity during processing were characterised by testing 5 different carbon fibre textiles and 4 different epoxy resins. Results showed that flow is affected strongly by the dual permeability of the textiles. In bulk RFI the use of lighter fabrics increased infusion time considerably while in interleaved RFI infusion time was mostly governed by yarn size. Despite the effect of dual scale permeability on resin flow, no voids were generated through flow separation. Instead, voids were caused either by wicking of low viscosity resins or by air trapped inside resin films prior to RFI processing. Bulk RFI enabled a reduction in void content over interleaved RFI because of longer flow distances that enabled extraction of trapped air.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin film infusion (RFI) is a manufacturing process developed in the 1980's for producing composites [1]. It consists of infusing hot-melt resin supplied as semi-solid films into dry textile reinforcements along their through-thickness direction. Two main RFI methods exist: bulk RFI and interleaved RFI.

Bulk RFI is the traditional method where semi-solid resin is placed on a textile preform. During processing resin melts, flows and saturates the preform. Bulk RFI was developed for mitigating some issues with other liquid composite moulding (LCM) techniques and prepreg part manufacturing; it forgoes most infusion ancillaries, features very short infusion distances and uses preforms that reduce lay-up labour [2].

Interleaved RFI is a newer variation that consists of consolidating lay-ups composed of dry textile plies interleaved with resin films [3]. It increases labour compared with bulk RFI but shorter infusion distances enable the use of toughened resins. Interleaved RFI was developed as an out-of-autoclave alternative to prepreg part manufacturing. In this case, void content is reduced by dry textiles that act as channels to remove gases instead of relying on high autoclave pressures to reduce voids. Interleaving can be achieved during lay-up; alternatively, commercial materials already interleaved are available in the form of partially impregnated textile reinforcements (semi-pregs).

Despite being available for some time, RFI is not characterised extensively. There is much discussion in the literature regarding macro-scale flow within preforms during RFI, where flow is assumed to obey Darcy's law within a uniform porous medium [4, 5]. However, there is very limited information about the effects of the dual permeability of textiles on resin flow. It is only recently that Cenders et al. characterised resin flow in and around yarns within weaves using semi-preg

materials [3]. Results showed that for their materials, resin saturated the inter-yarn regions first before saturating yarns along the fibre direction.

In this work, local resin flow is monitored in-situ during vacuum bag RFI processing, aiming at a better physical understanding of resin saturation and void formation within composites. Resin flow during both bulk and interleaved RFI is monitored at the surface of a composite lay-up using a camera. A wide selection of textiles including weaves and non-crimp fabrics and resins featuring different viscosities were tested towards proposing a more complete description of RFI.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Two epoxy-based resin formulations, RA and RB, featuring different viscosities were tested (Table 1). Functionalised carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were embedded and dispersed in some resin batches at a loading of 0.3wt% prior to filming for the purpose of increasing resin viscosity.

Five types of carbon fibre (HTS40, Toho-Tenax) textiles from Texonic and Saertex were tested (Table 2). The selection included one plain weave, two twills and two bidirectional $\pm 45^\circ$ non-crimp fabrics (NCFs), all featuring different surface densities.

Table 1: List of resin films			Table 2: List of textiles		
Code	CNT loading (wt%)	Viscosity at 60°C (Pa·s)	Code	Style	Surface density (g/m ²)
RA-1	0	190	PW-1	Plain weave	197
RA-2	0.3	260	TW-1	Twill 2×2	215
RB-1	0	61	TW-2	Twill 2×2	429
RB-2	0.3	-	NCF-1	Bidir. $\pm 45^\circ$	250
			NCF-2	Bidir. $\pm 45^\circ$	534

2.2 Processing

RFI experiments were conducted using out-of-autoclave vacuum bagging with direct heating of the tool. Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the set-up with the textile/resin film lay-up and ancillaries. Lay-ups measuring 10 cm by 10 cm in area were consolidated over a glass tool plate for monitoring resin flow at their surface. During processing, lay-ups were compacted at 1 bar. Heating was provided by an aluminium caul plate heated by a flexible silicone rubber heater (MINCO) controlled by a LabVIEW program. The imposed heating cycle lasted until resin gelation and consisted of heating up to a temperature of 130°C at a rate of 2°C/min, followed by a 2 hr dwell.

In interleaved RFI experiments a single resin film was interleaved between two textile plies. Bleeding was controlled at the edge of the lay-up through the use of sealant tape wrapped with a single ply of a glass fibre plain weave. Resins RA and RB were tested in interleaved RFI experiments.

In bulk RFI experiments all resin films and textile plies were grouped separately. Resin films infused from the top of the textile stack while bleeding occurred through the edge of the bottom-most textile ply. The bottom textile ply was larger than the others and connected to the breather, effectively acting as the bleeder. The remainder of the lay-up was sealed by sealant tape and release film. The number of textile plies was selected to lead to a consolidated laminate thickness of approximately 4 mm. It should be noted that due to limited resin availability, only resin RB was tested during bulk RFI experiments.

Figure 1: Vacuum bagging configuration for bulk and interleaved RFI flow monitoring experiments

2.3 Monitoring set-up and measurements

During RFI processing, images of resin flow at the surface of the lay-up were taken through a glass tool plate using a DSLR camera (D5100, Nikon) (Figure 2). A ring light was used as a source of non-directional lighting to limit yarn shadows. Images were taken with the camera every 20 seconds until resin gelation occurred. After the experiments, fill factors and porosity values at the surface of the stacks were measured through contrast image analysis. Fill factors FF were defined as the ratio of the image that was covered in resin, excluding the effect of porosity. Infusion time was defined as the time required for achieving a fill factor FF greater than 0.95.

Figure 2: Set-up for resin flow monitoring experiments

3 RESIN FLOW

3.1 Resin flow front progression

Interleaved RFI experiments showed that all combinations of textiles and resins led to comparable infusion stages (Figure 3). First resin flowed in gaps between yarns and stitches where permeability is greatest. After filling those gaps, resin filled yarns predominantly along fibre direction as opposed to the less permeable transverse direction. This behaviour is consistent with observations made by Cender et al. [3] who tested semi-preg materials at constant temperatures.

A relatively uniform flow front was observed in all experiments suggesting that for the interleaved stacking configuration, local variability in textile architecture does not affect resin flow strongly.

Figure 3: Typical resin fill factor progressions in plain weaves, twills and NCFs for interleaved RFI experiments

In most cases, bulk RFI experiments showed similar resin flow behaviour whereas resin first filled the inter-yarn gaps before filling yarns along the fibre direction (Figure 4). However, resin flow fronts were not uniform. This results from the increased number of textile plies which amplified the effect of local textile variability. This is a very important characteristic, as non-uniform flow fronts have increased odds of leading to air entrapment if breathing is not controlled adequately. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that in experiments conducted with the lighter NCF textile and RB resin, small zones could be observed where capillary flow across yarns and stitches preceded viscous flow in inter-yarn gaps. This occurred due to a combination of low resin viscosity and low textile permeability in the through-thickness direction. It is expected that capillary flow would become more dominant as infusion distances increase. Also, it is conjectured that a large difference in resistance to inter-yarn and intra-yarn resin flow may increase the risk of air entrapment in RFI.

Figure 4: Typical resin fill factor progressions in plain weaves, twills and NCFs for bulk RFI experiments

3.2 Infusion time

Infusion times required for saturating most of a single fabric ply with resin ($FF > 0.95$) for interleaved RFI varied from 18 min to more than 50 min depending on the combination of textile and resin (Figure 5). In all cases, infusion stopped before reaching dwell temperature.

Resin type influenced infusion time the most. Neat resins RA and RB procured similar infusion times. The addition of 0.3 wt% of CNTs increased the viscosity of resins and lengthened infusion.

Textile architecture also affected infusion. Infusion appeared to lengthen with an increase in textile surface density. This is explained by an increase in yarn size which leads to greater yarn volumes requiring filling under relatively lower permeability and to increased flow distances that delay saturation. In this work, surface density did not influence processing much as resin infusion was completed well before gelation; however it may become a limiting factor when using highly toughened resins which feature substantially higher viscosities, such as prepreg resins used in semi-preg materials. Aside from surface densities, other textile parameters likely affected infusion time, including the fabric cover factor and the yarn surface area in contact with resin.

Infusion times required for saturating 4 mm laminates with resin during bulk RFI varied from 32 min to 58 min (Figure 5). Interestingly, this was not considerably longer than saturation times observed with interleaved RFI despite the presence of up to 20 more textile plies. As a result, most infusions were completed before reaching the dwell temperature and well before resin gelation. This is attributed to the marked reduction in viscosity happening during the heating cycle.

Resin infusion was affected by the processing materials. On average, the addition of 0.3 wt% of CNTs lengthened infusion times by 19 %, which is consistent with the trend observed in interleaved RFI. A reduction by approximately half in textile surface density led to an increase in infusion times by 23 % and 45 % for NCFs and twills respectively. This decrease in permeability was caused by an increase in the number of textile plies required for achieving the same laminate thickness. Misalignment between plies forces resin to divert in-plane until it can reach a gap that would enable flow progression in the through-thickness direction. Increasing the number of plies increases obstacles that delay flow progression. Moreover, lighter weaves feature smaller crimp angles that enable better nesting between plies and reduce gap sizes, further limiting flow. From these results on thin laminates, it can be seen that material selection becomes crucial for ensuring complete saturation in large bulk RFI parts, before gelation occurs.

Figure 5: Infusion times for interleaved and bulk RFI based on the textile surface densities

4 VOID FORMATION DURING PROCESSING

4.1 Void formation

In this work, the effects of textile architecture on void kinetics during processing were investigated by using resin films that featured high levels of trapped air in their original state. Figure 6 shows the change in the air pocket structure during the heating cycle. Before RFI processing, minute pockets of trapped air were well dispersed throughout the resin films. As the process temperature increased, epoxy chains became more mobile and air pockets started to coalesce under the action of surface tension. Growing air pockets required space which compelled them to migrate towards the largest inter-yarn gaps. Air pocket migration occurred only when resin flowed.

Figure 6: Migration of air trapped inside resin film during processing

After migration, air pockets decreased in size until resin gelation (Figure 7). The smallest air pockets could collapse completely while the largest air pockets barely changed dimensions. No precise cause was confirmed as the source of this collapsing. It may have been caused by a combination of factors, but it is conjectured that air diffusing between epoxy chains played an important role. Diffusion occurs across the air-resin boundary and the collapsing rate of air pockets depends mostly on the surface area exposed to the resin. Smaller air pockets collapsed much quicker than larger ones because the surface-area-to-volume ratio increased with a reduction in volume.

The final void structure inside composites was defined by the remaining air pockets after gelation. Thus, efforts should be made towards minimising the size of air pockets, which would promote diffusion and decrease void content in final parts.

Figure 7: Air pocket size during processing a) after reaching dwell temperature and b) after gelation

4.1 Void content

Void contents varied greatly between composites featuring different combinations of resins, textiles and processing methods. Figure 8 shows that composites made of light weaves had the lowest void contents while those made of heavy weaves had the highest void content. This difference is attributed to the inter-yarn gap size that governs the air pocket size, which is proportional to the textile surface density. Conversely, no effect of textile surface density on void contents of composites made with NCFs could be confirmed with the current data. The smaller variation observed with NCFs is likely attributed to their inter-yarn gap size that is governed mostly by the stitch, which is the same for all NCFs tested.

Resin type affected void content but no clear trend could be identified. Variations are likely attributable to global and local difference in air content that is initially trapped in the resin films. It should be noted that void content values for several combinations of RB resin and NCFs are missing due to wicking that removed most resin from inter-yarn gaps. Wicking occurred due to a combination of factors: 1) RB resin featured the lowest viscosity, 2) NCFs feature unidirectional channels between yarns which promoted resin flow, and 3) infusion was completed long before resin gelation, leaving a long period where wicking was the sole driving force for resin flow.

Interleaved RFI generally resulted in a much higher void content than bulk RFI, with the exception of experiments made with the heavy twill. In bulk RFI, air pockets appeared at the flow front and burst to let air escape. These air pockets required a certain flow distance to overtake the resin flow fronts, enabling degassing. From low void content values in bulk RFI experiments, it follows that the through-thickness flow distance required for resin degassing was less than 4 mm for most textiles tested.

Figure 8: Surface void content measurements after gelation for interleaved and bulk RFI featuring various textiles and resins

Figure 9 shows that the reduction in air pocket size between the start of the temperature dwell and gelation was dependent on textile surface density. This behaviour was observed with both the interleaved and bulk RFI processes. It is conjectured that the effect of textile surface density may be related to the allowable air pocket size. As discussed above, smaller air pockets collapse more easily than larger ones due to diffusion.

Figure 9: Reduction of air pocket size between start of the dwell and resin gelation in interleaved and bulk RFI featuring various textiles and resins

5 CONCLUSION

In this work, resin flow and void formation during RFI processing were characterised for a wide selection of resin films and textiles. Two RFI processing methods were compared: interleaved and bulk configurations.

Resin infusion was marginally longer using bulk RFI as opposed to using interleaved RFI for fabricating laminates thinner than 4 mm. In interleaved RFI, infusion time increased with textile surface density due to greater flow distances. Conversely, large gaps between yarns facilitated infusion during bulk RFI.

Void formation was attributed to two causes: wicking and air trapped within resin films. The primary reason for wicking was low resin viscosity leading to low viscous forces compared with capillary forces. In the case of trapped air, it only moved with resin flow and required a certain flow distance to overtake the resin flow fronts. The greater flow distances in bulk RFI made it a superior method for degassing resin during processing. Ideally, resin films should be degassed prior to RFI processing. If this is not possible, voids can also be mitigated by using lighter textiles which limit air pocket size and promote void collapsing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Letterman L. E., 1986, "Resin film infusion process and apparatus", U.S. Patent 4622091, pp. 1–6.
- [2] Uchida H., Yamamoto T., and Takashima H., 2001, "Development of low-cost, damage resistant composites using RFI processing," *SAMPE J.*, 37(6), pp. 16–20.
- [3] Cender T. A., Simacek P., and Advani S. G., 2013, "Resin film impregnation in fabric prepregs with dual length scale permeability," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 53, pp. 118–128.
- [4] Han N., Suh S., Yang J., and Hahn H., 2003, "Resin film infusion of stitched stiffened composite panels," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, 34(3), pp. 227–236.
- [5] Loos A. . C., Rattazzi D., and Batra R. C., 2002, "A three-dimensional model of the resin film infusion process," *J. Compos. Mater.*, 36(10), pp. 1255–1273.